

Assessing Carbon Payback Time of Replacements and Refurbishments in Zurich's Residential Buildings (2001–2019) Using Stock-Level CRLCA

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Keywords: building replacement and refurbishment; consequential replacement LCA (CRLCA); carbon payback time; residential buildings; range-bound analysis; per capita metric.

ABSTRACT. Under Switzerland's *inward development* policy, building replacement (BR) has become a prevalent strategy to urban renewal—yet its assumed advantage in delivering greater carbon savings over refurbishment is increasingly questioned. Refurbishment, defined as the preservation and continued use of existing buildings, is commonly framed as a circular economy practice. To identify the environmentally preferable strategy, this study evaluates the carbon payback time (CPBT) of replacement versus refurbishment in Zurich's residential buildings, using Consequential Replacement Life Cycle Assessment (CRLCA). CRLCA, as proposed by Huuhka et al. (2023) [1], isolates the post-decision carbon emissions resulting from replacement or retention choices by excluding historical and unaffected ones, enabling comparisons that reflect outcomes subject to strategic influence. This study extends CRLCA to the building stock level to enable a more representative evaluation than individual-building assessments. To operationalize this extension, two modeling methods are introduced: using a unified decision year to align projects with varying implementation timelines, enabling consistent evaluation of how decision timing influences CPBT outcomes; and estimating carbon emissions under optimistic and conservative assumptions, reflecting lower and upper bounds of key emission factors, to assess the sensitivity of CPBT outcomes. Moreover, a per capita metric complements the conventional per area approach, capturing both building-level and user-level carbon intensity.

The analysis draws on 335 residential BR projects completed in Zurich between 2001 and 2019 as the baseline scenario, and constructs two counterfactual refurbishment scenarios for comparison. The system boundaries follow the post-decision logic of CRLCA and include embodied (A1–A5, B5, C1) and operational (B6, B7) emissions related to heating demand, as defined by EN 15978. Four reference years (2010, 2013, 2016, 2019) are tested to explore the effect of policy timing, with 2013 closely aligning with actual implementation. Results show that CPBT is highly sensitive to both decision timing and metric selection. BR consistently exhibits the highest embodied and lowest operational emissions on a per-unit basis. Even under optimistic assumptions, BR only achieves payback before 2019; after that, it fails by either metric as decarbonization erodes the operational advantage of new buildings. This pattern extends to public buildings, where higher embodied impacts from more intensive construction, combined with lower operational demand per unit area, further disadvantage BR. Refurbishment proves more climate-conscious, overturning the assumption of greater carbon savings from replacement. Moreover, per capita metrics consistently yield more conservative results than per area metrics under identical conditions, demonstrating how metric choice shapes outcomes. The result highlights the value of per capita analysis in revealing individual carbon responsibility and fostering participatory, citizen-focused policymaking. Taken together, the study underscores the time-critical nature of construction policies for climate mitigation and adaptation, calling for continual reassessment as conditions evolve. It further emphasizes that the climate benefit from lifespan extension within circular construction is vital to advancing sustainability.

[1] S. Huuhka, M. Moisisio, E. Salmio, A. Köliö, and J. Lahdensivu, "Renovate or replace? Consequential replacement LCA framework for buildings," *Buildings and Cities*, vol. 4, no. 1, pp. 212–228, 2023.

*The author, independent scholar, formerly at EPFL: emilyyip1129@gmail.com. CSC-funded (201808310110). Thanks to Prof. Satu Huuhka for review and guidance, and to Prof. Corentin Fivet for official support.